

On the Nature of Charge Injecting Contacts in Organic Field-Effect Transistors

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ABSTRACT

Organic field-effect transistors (OFETs) are key enabling devices for plastic electronics technology, which has a potentially disruptive impact on a variety of application fields, such as

health, safety and communication. Despite the tremendous advancements in understanding the OFET working mechanisms and device performance, further insight into the complex correlation between the nature of the charge injecting contacts and the electrical characteristics of devices is still necessary. Here, an in-depth study of the metal-organic interfaces that provides a direct correlation to the performance of OFET devices is reported.

The combination of synchrotron x-ray spectroscopy, atomic force microscopy, electron microscopy, and theoretical simulations on two selected electron transport organic semiconductors with tailored chemical structures allows to gain insight on the nature of the injecting contacts. This multiple analysis repeated at the different stages of contact formation provides a clear picture on the synergy between organic/metal interactions, interfacial morphology and structural organization of the electrode. The simultaneous synchrotron x-ray experiments and electrical measurements of OFETs *in operando* uncovers how the nature of the charge injecting contacts has a direct impact on the injection potential of OFETs.

INTRODUCTION

Organic field-effect transistors (OFETs) have gained considerable attention in the last decades since they are key components of the emerging organic electronics platform which offers, compared to the inorganic counterpart, distinguishing properties such as flexibility, light weight, chemical tailoring of the functional materials, and low-cost manufacturing.^{1,2}

A huge amount of work has been devoted to the investigation and optimization of the OFET fundamental sub-components with the final aim to gain a deep understanding of the device working mechanisms and performance.^{3,4} In particular, the design and chemical synthesis of a variety of organic semiconductors (OSCs) with tailored properties,^{5,6,7,8} the development of

highly performing and multifunctional gate dielectrics^{9,10} and the comprehension of the central role of the interface between the dielectric and the active materials^{4,11,12} significantly contributed to uncover the potential of OFETs as an enabling breakthrough technology in a variety of application fields, such as health, sensing, and information and communications technology (ICT).^{13,14}

However, a persistent weakness of the device platform lies in the charge injecting contacts that limit the device performance and affect the technology reliability.¹⁵ Indeed, the correlation between the nature of the charge injecting contacts and the device operation is a complex topic that is still under debate.^{16,17} As widely reported in the literature,¹⁸ charge injection processes are not exclusively regulated by the energy mismatch between the Fermi level of the metal and the transport electronic levels of the semiconductor.^{19,20,21} Other factors, like chemical reactions and the formation of metal clusters on the semiconductor surface, are among the elements that influence metal/organic interfaces and determine the nature of the charge injecting contacts.^{22,23,24}

Photoelectron spectroscopy has been extensively used to understand the chemical and electronic properties of metals deposited onto perylene derivatives,²⁵ thiophene-based semiconductors²⁶ and phthalocyanines.^{27,28} It has been demonstrated that the chemistry of both the metal and the semiconductor plays a relevant role in the formation of the interface. Nevertheless, additional parameters, such as surface morphology, must be considered to properly describe injection barriers. For instance, OSC-on-metal and metal-on-OSC are systems with drastically different interfacial properties because of their morphological and microstructural differences.²⁹

As a matter of fact, a complete study of the interplay of the different factors that contribute to the formation of the OSC/metal interface is necessary to understand the nature of the charge injecting contacts and its effects on the operation of OFET devices.

Here, we report a thorough investigation of the metal-organic interfaces and show how the nature of the charge injecting contacts affects the electrical characteristics of OFET devices. We investigated top-contact transistor architectures, that typically provide higher charge injection efficacy,³⁰ and compared two carefully selected electron-transport OSC materials endowed with a tailored chemical composition to provide clear insight on the effect of chemical reactions at the organic-metal interface. Selected organic semiconductors were a perylene derivative (*i.e.* N,N'-ditridecylperylene-3,4,9,10-tetracarboxylic diimide, known as PTCDI-C13 or **P13**)³¹ and a thieno(bis)imide end-substituted quaterthiophene (*i.e.* 2,2'-(2,2'-bithiophene-5,5'-diyl)bis(5-butyl-5H-thieno[2,3-c]pyrrole-4,6)-dione, known as **NT4N**),^{32,33,34,35} while gold was used as benchmark noble metal for the injecting electrodes, also in view of its rich coordination chemistry at the nanometer-scale that makes it especially suitable for x-ray spectroscopic analysis.³⁶

It is important to note that both selected molecules are characterized by frontier orbitals with similar energy^{15,37} and the same energy levels alignment with gold, which predicts the same charge injection barriers at the contacts. The different heteroatoms in the chemical structures and the n-type field-effect behaviour of P13 and NT4N are key features that make this comparative work of broad and general interest.

Specifically, highly-sensitive and atom-selective synchrotron x-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS: namely Extended X-ray Absorption Fine Structure, EXAFS, and X-ray Absorption Near-

Edge Spectroscopy, XANES) combined with theoretical simulations, provided a clear picture of the physical chemistry of the OSC/metal interface at the nanoscale level.

Furthermore, an in-depth morphological and structural analysis on the process of electrode formation onto the OSC layer, at different Au thicknesses, was carried out by means of atomic force microscopy (AFM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The correlation of the chemical and structural information and the results of synchrotron XAS experiments performed on OFETs *in-operando*, shed light on the stability of the contact interface and on the efficacy of charge injection. The voltage drop at the injecting contacts was quantified from the n-type electrical characteristics of the devices, which clarified how the nature of the contact rules the OFET performance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The OFET architecture used in this work is reported in Figure 1a. All devices were fabricated onto a glass/Indium Tin Oxide (ITO) substrate covered by poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) as gate dielectric layer. NT4N and P13 (Figure 1b) were used as different OSC materials and gold was used for both source and drain electrodes. Except for the deposition condition of the two OSC compounds, the fabrication protocol was kept the same. NT4N and P13 layers were deposited by using the optimized nominal thickness of each to guarantee the best OFET performance.^{10,38}

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the OFET architecture (a) and chemical structures of P13 and NT4N used as OSC layer (b).

In order to investigate the physicochemical interactions that occur at the OSC/electrode interface, XAS analyses (*i.e.* Au L₃-edge EFAXS and XANES) were carried out on both NT4N- and P13-based OFETs. Specifically, the gold chemical states were examined at different electrode thicknesses, from 2 nm to 15 nm, to analyse the first stages of contact formation.

Figure 2 shows L₃-edge Fourier transform EXAFS (FT-EXAFS) spectra of NT4N- and P13-based OFETs.

A fitting procedure applied to raw data allowed to evaluate: *i*) the nearest-neighbor length (R_1) between gold atoms,³⁹ *ii*) the Debye–Waller factor (σ^2), that is an indicator of the level of disorder in the neighbor distance, and *iii*) the size of possible clusters (D).⁴⁰ All the obtained values are reported in the Supporting Information (Table S1 and S2).

Figure 2. Au L₃-edge FT-EXAFS spectra (red line) and model (black line) of gold electrodes, at different thicknesses, grown on NT4N (a) and P13 (b) in complete OFET devices. The EXAFS signal from an Au foil is reported as a reference.

Table 1. Au L₃-EDGE EXAFS fitting results from a reference Au foil and an Au electrode on NT4N- and P13-based OFETs, respectively. The thickness of the Au electrode is 2 nm.

	<i>Au foil</i>	<i>NT4N/Au</i>	<i>P13/Au</i>
CN₁	12	9.8	9.5
R₁ [Å]	2.879	2.850	2.846
σ²₁ [Å²]	0.0027	0.0035	0.0044
R_{Au-S} [Å]	-	2.23	-

Independently of the electrode thickness and the OSC compound (Figure 2), a reduction of the first Au-Au average coordination number (CN₁) emerged for all OFETs in comparison to a reference Au foil. In particular, in the case of a 2-nm thick Au layer (Table 1), CN₁ passed from 12, in the Au foil,⁴¹ to 9.8 and 9.5 for NT4N- and P13-based devices, respectively.

Moreover, both OSC/Au systems showed: *i*) a contraction of the Au-Au length, from 2.879 Å in the Au foil to 2.850 Å and 2.846 Å for NT4N and P13, respectively; *ii*) an enhanced disorder, as

evidenced by the increased Debye-Waller factor (σ^2) (Table 1). These results indicate the presence of clustered Au atoms on both the analysed OSCs, in agreement with what has been already demonstrated.^{42,43}

To investigate the process of electrode formation, the dimension of gold nanoclusters (D) as a function of the Au nominal thickness was calculated by following the method reported in the literature.⁴⁴ As shown in Table 2, when Au is deposited on top of P13, gold nanoclusters rapidly expand from 22 Å to 50 Å by increasing the gold layer thickness from 2 nm to 5 nm. By further depositing Au to reach a 15 nm-thick layer, D remains almost constant.

Conversely, when Au is deposited on top of NT4N, the increase of D as a function of the thickness is more gradual in comparison to the growth of Au on P13.

Table 2. Gold nanocluster dimension (D) as a function of the Au electrode thickness deposited on top of a NT4N- or P13-based OFET.

Au thickness [nm]	Au cluster dimension – D [Å]	
	NT4N	P13
2	24	22
5	38	50
10	43	46
15	42	47

The slight variation between NT4N/Au and P13/Au, in terms of the arrangement of gold atoms during the deposition, suggests that the nanocluster forming process may be ruled by a different type of interaction occurring at the OSC/Au interface.

In this context, it is worth mentioning that the deposition of Au electrodes on perylenes similar to P13 has been demonstrated to form Au nanoclusters on the OSC layer, on which a physisorption process has been proven to occur.²⁵

However, considering that even noble metals could show chemical reactivity at the nanoscale level,⁴⁵ the different chemical structure of the two OSCs could play a major role in determining the nature of interaction with the nanostructured electrode.

NT4N, contrarily to P13, is an oligothiophene characterized by presence of thienyl-rings sulphur atoms. The strong chemical affinity between Au and S is well known.³⁶ As a matter of fact, the goodness of the fitting procedure applied to the FT-EXAFS analysis of NT4N-based OFETs is ensured only when using a model including Au-S chemical interactions (Figure S1). In addition to that, independently of the Au thickness, a slight shift of the peak in the region around 2 Å (Figure 2a) is revealed in comparison to that of the Au foil, that is also an indication of the chemical interaction between NT4N sulphur atoms and Au nanoclusters with an average distance of 2.23 Å (Table 1).⁴⁶ In agreement with that, FT-EXAFS measurements on P13-based OFETs (Figure 2b) did not show any modification in the region around 2 Å. Furthermore, the use of models of fitting including Au-heteroatom interactions reduced the quality of the fit (Table S2). A further confirmation was found in XANES spectra (Figure 3). XANES refers to an x-ray spectral region that provides chemical information including charge transfer processes. Thus, an in-depth analysis on the oxidation state of gold nanoclusters on NT4N was carried out at different Au thicknesses.

Figure 3. Au L_3 XANES data relative to gold electrode at different thicknesses growth on a) NT4N OSC and b) P13 OSC. The arrows indicate the zooms and the spectra variation with respect to the gold metal foil. The XANES signal from Au metal foil is reported as a reference. $E_0 = 11919$ eV.

As shown in the inset of Figure 3a, an increase of the intensity of the shoulder peak at relative energies around 6 eV ($E_0 = 11919$ eV), that can be associated to a $2p_{3/2} \rightarrow 5d$ transition, is observed at each Au thickness.

Typically, from the formal electronic configurations of gold, *i.e.* Au^0 ($5d^{10} 6s^1$), Au^{1+} ($5d^{10} 6s^0$), and Au^{3+} ($5d^8 6s^0$), only Au^{3+} is supposed to exhibit the $2p_{3/2} \rightarrow 5d$ transition. Nevertheless, in real conditions, the proximity between the Au 5d and 6s levels can cause the orbital mixing and the d-orbital vacancy even in Au^0 or Au^{1+} states, thus allowing the $2p_{3/2} \rightarrow 5d$ transition. By increasing unoccupied d orbitals, the corresponding peak in XANES spectra is typically more intense. For instance, the interaction of gold ions with sulphur ions is known to decrease the number of occupied d states of Au^0 .⁴⁷ Hence, the increase of the shoulder peak that we observe near 6 eV ($2p_{3/2} \rightarrow 5d$ transition) (Figure 3a), independently from the Au thickness, can be

correlated to a partial oxidation of gold clusters, that are positively charged.⁴² This indicates a certain degree of electron transfer from gold nanoclusters to thienyl sulphur atoms of the NT4N molecule, which confirms the existence of an Au-S chemical interaction between NT4N and the nanostructured gold electrode, as similarly reported for other systems.^{42,45} Despite an electron transfer in the opposite direction (*i.e.* from sulphur to gold) is typically expected to occur,⁴⁸ gold at the nanoscale have a significantly different electronic structure than bulk gold. Indeed, a transfer of electron-density from Au nanoparticles to sulphur has been already demonstrated.⁴⁹

The interaction of Au with sulphur atoms of NT4N is also evidenced by the enhancement of the intensity at 16 eV in comparison with the foil of gold, as similarly reported for thiol-protected Au nanoparticles.⁵⁰

Also, by focusing on the regions around 26 eV and 51 eV, the shift of the two bands to higher energies confirms the presence of metal clusters,³⁹ in accordance with the FT-EXAFS spectra reported in Figure 2.

For the sake of completeness, XANES spectra were also recorded on P13-based OFETs (Figure 3b). As expected, the spectra at different Au thicknesses resulted perfectly overlapping that of the Au metal foil in the spectral region related to the Au-S bond, *i.e.* from the edge to 16 eV above the edge (inset of Figure 3b). According to what found for NT4N-based OFETs, a spectral shift associated to the Au nanocluster formation was also observed.

In view of correlating the physicochemical interactions at NT4N/Au and P13/Au interfaces to the early stages of formation of the electrodes, theoretical simulations were carried out.

In detail, the initial step relevant to the formation of the organic/metal interface can be described as the interaction between a gold atom, approaching the organic layer, and a molecule. In the regime of weak intermolecular coupling,⁵¹ as commonly observed in organic materials, the

organic/metal interface can be approximated by a convolution of isolated molecular electronic states interacting with metal aggregates. Further details are reported in the Experimental Section. Figure 4 shows the maps of the spatial distribution of the binding energy between a gold atom and NT4N and P13 molecules.

Figure 4. Volume map of the gold-molecule binding energy (Hartrees) computed at the PM6 level on a regular mesh of grid points for NT4N (left panel) and P13 (right panel). 1 Ha corresponds to 27.21 eV.

As evidenced by the regions with relatively high binding energy, NT4N exhibits preferential adsorption sites for gold atoms in close proximity of thiophyl sulphur atoms, that further corroborates the results obtained by XANES. Diversely, the gold-molecule binding energy is much lower for P13, with no evidence of favored adsorption configurations. Indeed, the volume map of P13/Au in Figure 4 is one among different volume maps obtained by repeating the computational analysis.

The computed gold-molecule binding energy for the lowest-energy density functional theory (DFT) optimized configuration amounts respectively to 0.65 eV and 0.39 eV for NT4N and P13, in agreement with the Au-S strength expected in similar systems.⁵² Also, the computed gold-sulphur distance resulted 2.30 Å, that is well-comparable with respect to FT-EXAFS fitting parameters (*i.e.* 2.23 Å) and with the literature.⁵³

In order to mimic the formation of a molecule/gold interface during the early stages of the deposition of the metal onto the organic thin-film, the number of gold atoms in contact with the NT4N molecule was progressively increased. The most favorable configuration after the addition of five gold atoms (Figure S2) clearly shows the first stage of formation of gold nanoclusters in the proximity of the thienyl sulphur atom, in agreement with XAS analyses and with previous works.⁵⁴

In summary, XAS data and computational simulations are in line to prove the presence of electrostatic force at the nanostructured gold organic/electrode interface in P13-based OFETs and, conversely, orbital hybridization at the organic/nanostructured gold electrode interface in NT4N-based OFETs. This study highlights that the interfacial interaction/strength is extremely different and induces a chemisorbed electrode on top of the NT4N OSC with respect to a physisorbed electrode on top of the P13 OSC.

The resulting difference of interaction, in terms of type and strength, between NT4N/Au and P13/Au interfaces may also have an impact on the growth process of the electrodes and on the mechanisms of charge injection of the two different OFETs.

Aiming at elucidating the influence of injecting contacts on operating devices, it is worth mentioning that OFETs typically require bulky electrodes (*e.g.* 70 nm thick) to ensure an optimal device operation. Hence, the process of electrode growth and formation, from the first layers to

the bulk, needs to be analyzed. As already reported, we experimentally studied the first stages of electrode formation (up to 15 nm) by means of the highly sensitive XAS with the support of computational simulations. To shed light on the characteristics of the contacts with their final thickness, we also investigated the surface morphology of 25 nm- and 70 nm-thick electrodes via AFM.

The surface morphology of bare NT4N and P13 OSC layers, within the complete OFET platform, was first analysed (Figure 5a and 5b). In agreement with our precedent works,^{33,55,56} the surface morphology of the two OSCs was significantly different.

Figure 5. AFM images (1 $\mu\text{m} \times 1 \mu\text{m}$) of NT4N (a) and P13 (b) OSC layers in complete OFETs. Corresponding AFM images measured on a 25 nm (c, d) and 70 nm-thick gold electrode (e, f), respectively for NT4N (c, e) and P13 (d, f). The inset in panel (c) shows a magnification of the selected (200 nm \times 200 nm) area and a tenfold expansion of the Z-scale. For NT4N, S_q values are 25.3 ± 5.5 nm, 19.8 ± 5.2 nm and 17.7 ± 8.3 nm respectively for bare NT4N (a),

NT4N/Au(25 nm) (c) and NT4N/Au(70 nm) (e). For P13, S_q values are 2.5 ± 0.1 nm, 2.1 ± 0.3 nm and 3.1 ± 0.4 nm respectively for bare P13 (b), P13/Au(25 nm) (d) and P13/Au(70 nm) (f).

SEM images (500 nm x 500 nm) of a 70 nm-thick gold electrode on NT4N (g) and P13 (h).

The NT4N surface appeared as composed by a 3D growth of overlapped, elongated flakes few hundreds of nanometers in length (Figure 5a). Conversely, the surface morphology of the P13 layer was characterized by a more ordered and mainly 2D growth of islands, with significantly smaller lateral sizes, approximately tens of nanometers (Figure 5b).

According to that, the root-mean-square height area roughness (S_q) was measured to be 25.3 ± 5.5 nm and 2.5 ± 0.1 nm for NT4N and P13, respectively.

AFM micrographs of the Au layer on the NT4N/Au(25 nm) (Figure 5c) and P13/Au(25nm) (Figure 5d) stacks did not show significant S_q differences with respect to corresponding topographic images of pristine OSC layers (Figure 5a and 5b): S_q NT4N/Au(25nm) = 19.8 ± 5.2 nm (Figure 5c), S_q P13/Au(25nm) = 2.1 ± 0.3 nm (Figure 5d). On a qualitative level, the surface of the NT4N/Au(25 nm) stack appeared to be very similar to that of the corresponding pristine OSC, where elongated flakes are the most prominent surface feature. In contrast, the morphology of the P13/Au(25 nm) stack resulted different from that of bare P13, showing the typical granular characteristics of pure evaporated Au.

Nonetheless, we expected to find the evidence of Au nanoclusters on the surface of NT4N and P13 layers, as indicated by the previous XAS analyses. A more thorough morphological inspection of NT4N/Au(25 nm) revealed that the elongated structures were densely decorated by nanosized grains (inset of Figure 5c). In addition, AFM phase images of NT4N/Au(25 nm) (Figure S3c) and P13/Au(25 nm) (Figure S3d) clearly showed the presence, on both OSCs

surfaces, of nanosized grains, while those are completely absent in phase images collected in the same way on pristine OSCs (Figure S3a and S3b).

These observations are compatible with the formation of Au nanoclusters on both OSC surfaces during the deposition of 25 nm-thick electrodes. In this context, qualitative morphological differences between the electrodes of NT4N- and P13-based devices can be ascribed to the different S_q values of (bare) NT4N and P13 layers. Since the measured S_q of the P13 layer is one order of magnitude smaller than the Au thickness ($S_q = 2.5$ nm, Au thickness = 25 nm), the electrode completely covers the underlying OSC features thus forming a continuous layer which substantially exposes a bulk gold surface. Conversely, the NT4N layer has a S_q value similar to the nominal thickness of the evaporated Au electrode ($S_q = 25.3$ nm, Au thickness = 25 nm). Due to this, the 25-nm thick gold layer does not completely mimic the OSC morphology and is, as a consequence, more fragmented even at full coverage. This observation can also help in rationalizing why the best performances in NT4N-based devices were obtained when using a thicker Au electrode, *i.e.* ≥ 70 nm.^{32,33}

To corroborate the above observations, we explored the surface morphologies of NT4N/Au(70 nm) and P13/Au(70 nm) stacks, in which the electrode thickness was increased to 70 nm. It is worthy to remark that all the measurements were performed on complete devices.

AFM micrographs of the Au layer on the NT4N/Au(70 nm) and P13/Au(70nm) stacks did not show significant S_q differences with respect to bare OSC layers, similarly to what observed for samples with 25 nm-thick gold electrodes: S_q NT4N/Au(70nm) = 17.7 ± 8.3 nm (Figure 5e), S_q P13/Au(70nm) = 3.1 ± 0.4 nm (Figure 5f).

The surface of the P13/Au(70 nm) stack (Figure 5f) showed a granular morphology with an increased Au grain average size with respect to P13/Au(25 nm) (Figure 5d). This finding is

substantiated by the corresponding AFM phase images (Figure S3d and S3f) and SEM images (Figure 5h). It is reasonable to suppose that Au nanoclusters present on P13/Au(25 nm) gradually merge into bigger aggregates upon further Au evaporation. Due to the weak interaction between Au and P13, the formation of larger Au nanoclusters would reduce the total energy of the system, in agreement with theoretical predictions.⁵⁴

Concerning the morphology of NT4N/Au(70 nm) (Figure 5e), the elongated flakes typical of the bare OSC surface (Figure 5a) resulted to be almost completely covered by further deposition of Au (*i.e.* from 25 nm to 70nm). In accordance to what observed on NT4N/Au(25 nm), AFM phase images are indicative of Au nanoclusters covering the exposed device surface (Figure S3e).

Interestingly, high-resolution SEM analyses of NT4N/Au(70 nm) (Figure 5g) evidenced a high degree of decoration of the NT4N flakes with Au nanoclusters with an approximate average diameter of ~10 nm, in agreement with the nanocluster dimensions obtained from EXAFS analyses (Table 2).

A direct comparison of P13/Au and NT4N/Au morphologies reveals a higher tendency of NT4N to immobilize gold clusters during the electrode growth, which result to be smaller than the clusters present on the P13 layer. This observation is compatible with the existence of a stronger interaction between Au and NT4N, as demonstrated by XAS and computational analyses (Figure 3 and 4). The relatively rough surface of NT4N in conjunction with the physicochemical interactions between NT4N and Au hampers Au clusters to merge during the first stages of Au deposition. Diversely, the smoother surface of P13 and the weak interactions between P13 and Au favour the coalescence of Au clusters. Interfacial morphology and physicochemical interactions are indeed strongly correlated in defining the nature of the OSC/Au interface.

It can thus be concluded that the nature of the interactions at the OSC/Au interface in conjunction with the surface morphology of the pristine OCS layers plays a major role on the process of formation and structural organization of the electrode, in full agreement with the growth model of gold contacts on similar systems that has been recently proposed.⁵⁷

To better understand the impact of the Au/OSC interface on the OFET operation, we assessed the reliability of the reported results also in operating devices. Despite the typical electric field of operating OFETs is not expected to drastically affect chemical bonds,⁵⁸ the operational parameters of OFET, such as the contact resistance, are strongly dependent on the gate voltage.⁵⁹

In this regard, XAS has been already used to analyze the bond length variation in metal clusters under external stress.^{43,60} Hence, we repeated EXAFS and XANES measurements on OFETs both in OFF and ON states and at different operating regimes (linear and saturation).

To the best of our knowledge, these studies have never been performed before. For this type of tests, the Au thickness should be minimized in order to allow XAS analyses. Therefore, we reduced the thickness to 25 nm in order to guarantee the operation of the devices while allowing to reveal the OSC/Au interface contribution via XAS. We first assessed, via XAS, that the characteristics of a 15 nm-thick Au layer are similar to those of a 25 nm-thick Au electrode. Accordingly, OFETs with a 25 nm-thick electrode showed a XANES spectrum overlapping that of OFETs with a 15-nm thick Au layer (Figure S4).

Despite the optimal performance of the corresponding devices is typically obtained at Au thickness of 70 nm, we also proved that good FET characteristics are ensured by using 25 nm-thick Au electrodes (Figure S5). The use of a 25 nm-thick electrode therefore results the best trade-off to carry out XAS analyses on operating devices.

By driving the corresponding OFETs in linear and subsequently in saturation regime (as usually done during standard electrical characterizations), EXAFS and XANES were carried out (Figure 6). More details are provided in the Experimental Section.

The application of gate-source (V_{GS}) and drain-source (V_{DS}) biases up to 100 V to NT4N-based OFETs did not show any influence on the XANES spectra (Figure 6a). Indeed, if comparing the analysis on OFETs in OFF state and ON states, in both linear regime and in saturation regimes, XANES spectra resulted perfectly superposed.

Similarly, the interface between Au and P13 resulted stable under the applied bias (Figure 6b).

For the sake of completeness, the analysis was repeated on both source and drain electrodes, since the effect of the electric field on charge injection and extraction interfaces may differ. Nevertheless, by comparing the results, no differences were revealed (Figure 6b). From the fitting procedure applied to raw data, the gold nanocluster dimension resulted ≈ 50 Å at both contacts (Table S3 and S4), in agreement with XAS results on P13-devices comprising 15 nm-thick electrodes (Table 2 and Table S2).

Figure 6. a) XANES spectra of NT4N-based OFETs in OFF state (black line) and n-type ON state in linear (red dotted line) and saturation (green dotted line) regimes. b) EXAFS spectra of P13-based OFET devices in OFF and ON state with a focus on drain (left panel) and source (right panel) electrodes.

This suggests that the applied electric field does not alter the nature of the organic metal interface: if any variations are present, they are below the detection limit.

In view of understanding how the interface of injecting contacts determines the electrical performance of OFETs, we preliminarily evaluated the energy level alignments at the NT4N/Au

and P13/Au interfaces. As reported in literature,^{15,37} the two OSC compounds present a similar energy of the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) at around -3.4 eV, while the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) resulted -6.0 eV and -5.4 eV respectively for NT4N and P13. In the case of n-type OFETs, the conduction of free carriers occurs via LUMO levels.^{31,61} Hence, if the Au Fermi level is compared to the LUMO level of NT4N or to that of P13, the charge injection efficacy is expected to be similar for both cases.

The similar energy alignment between the two molecular semiconductors and the metal contact allows associating putative differences in the OFET operation to the specific nature of the injecting contact.

In this regard, the n-type electrical characteristics of the corresponding OFETs with 70 nm-thick Au electrode were measured and compared.

In agreement with the literature,^{10,55} the resulting devices demonstrated a good operation under n-type polarization, with an electron field-effect mobility (μ_{FET}) of 0.5 cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹ and 0.1 cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹ for NT4N- and P13-based OFETs, respectively (Figure S6 and S7). These data were estimated from the saturation regime using the following equation to have a figure-of-merit (FOM) representative of the devices:

$$I_{DS} = \frac{1}{2} C_i \frac{W}{L} \mu_{FET} (V_{GS} - V_T)^2$$

In detail, C_i is the capacitance per unit area of the insulating layer, W and L are the width and the length of the channel, respectively, and V_T is the threshold voltage extracted from the square root of the drain-source current ($I_{DS}^{1/2}$) versus V_{GS} characteristics.

The values of the estimated equivalent lumped resistance (computed for $V_{GS} = V_{DS} = 100$ V) resulted about 6k Ω and 600 Ω for NT4N- and P13-based OFETs, respectively.

However, to quantitatively evaluate the impact of the OSC/Au interface, we used a single-transistor method developed by Torricelli et al.,⁶² that enables to quantify the contact voltage drop directly from multiple standard output characteristics of a single OFET.

More specifically, we extracted the injection voltages (V_J) as a function of V_{GS} for both NT4N- and P13-based OFETs (Figure 7a and 7b) which represents the voltage at the metal contact required for the injection of charges.

This approach allows for a direct measurement of the contact potential in real working devices and hence possible changes of the electron injection barrier, as a consequence of the applied electric field, the temperature of operation, etc.,⁶³ are considered.

NT4N-based devices showed a V_J that is one order of magnitude greater than P13-based devices (*e.g.* at $V_{GS} = V_{DS} = 100V$, $V_J \approx 6V$ and $V_J \approx 0.8V$ for NT4N and P13, respectively), independently from V_{GS} . Hence, a higher voltage drop at the contact is evidenced at the NT4N/Au interface in comparison to P13/Au. To note, the V_J value obtained from NT4N-based devices results in agreement with the voltage drop for the injection of electrons extracted via optical methods, *i.e.* $V_J \approx 6V$.¹⁵

Figure 7. Injection voltages (V_J) as a function of V_{GS} derived from a) NT4N- and b) P13-based OFETs by using the Torricelli method; I_{DS} current as a function of V_J estimated from c) NT4N- and d) P13-based OFETs.

In addition to that, as shown in Figure 7c and 7d, the I_{DS} as a function of V_J reported different behaviors. In fact, in P13-based OFETs, the almost linear increase of I_{DS} with V_J is characterized by relatively high currents (hundreds of μ A) at relatively low injecting voltages (< 1V). In comparison, the exponential increase reported for NT4N-based OFETs showed lower I_{DS} at a higher V_J (tens of μ A at 6V).

This further confirms the hampered injection at the NT4N/Au interface, that can be therefore correlated to the nature of interactions occurring at the contacts. Indeed, if considering that both NT4N- and P13-based OFETs are characterized by similar FOMs, *e.g.* LUMO energies,

transistor architecture, OSC mobility, etc., the origin of the different voltage drop at the contacts can be evidently ascribed to the different nature of metal/organic interactions.

For the sake of clarity, we remind that NT4N and P13 OSC layers present different thickness in the corresponding OFET, because each device has been independently optimized. Since the contact potential may be also dependent on the OSC layer thickness,⁶⁴ OFETs including P13 or NT4N with similar OSC layer thickness, *i.e.* 75 nm, were fabricated and their electrical response was measured. As shown in Figure S8, in comparison to P13-devices, the n-type output characteristics of NT4N-based OFETs showed an I_{DS} with pronounced S-shape in the linear regime (at V_{DS} between 0 V and 10 V), that is typical correlated to a hampered injection at contacts.⁶²

Despite the efficacy of electron-injection from the metal to the OSC was predicted to be similar for NT4N/Au and P13/Au interfaces due to the energy-level alignment, the significant probability to find the LUMO of NT4N on thienyl sulphur atoms⁶⁵ in conjunction with the presence of Au-S chemical interactions and the formation of nanoclustered Au electrodes introduce factors that affect the process of electron injection. For instance, possible hybridization at the vicinity of the Au Fermi level, charge redistribution or the presence of chemisorption induced gap states are among the possible factors that influence the barriers for electron-injection.^{66,67} The possibility of diffusion of single Au atoms or very small clusters into the OSC acting as carrier traps, that is typical of systems in which gold electrodes are thermally evaporated on organic films,²⁵ may also contribute to the differences between NT4N/Au and P13/Au interfaces. Furthermore, sulphur-metal junctions have been demonstrated not to be good mediators of wave function at the Fermi energy, that is indeed related to the tunnel probability.⁶⁷ Despite the detailed mechanism of electron injection at the OSC/Au interface is beyond the

scope of this work, estimations of the height of the electron injection barrier can further help in understanding the processes involved at electrode contacts. More specifically, UPS analyses on OFETs based on P13, as OSC, and Au, as top source and drain electrodes, revealed an electron injection barrier of 0.2 eV,⁶⁸ in agreement with the low injecting voltages that we previously reported (Figure 7b). To evaluate the NT4N/Au injection barrier, we can consider gold at the contact with α,ω -dihexyl-quaterthiophene (DH4T) as a reasonably comparative system because of the similarity of the two OSCs and their similar chemical interaction with gold.⁶⁹ A difference of 0.85 eV was measured *via* UPS between the Au Fermi energy and the energy of the DH4T HOMO level. By considering that DH4T and NT4N have HOMO levels with similar energy and that the optical band gap of NT4N is 2.6 eV, the electron injection barrier at the NT4N/Au interface results around 1.75 eV. The estimated electron injection barriers at the P13/Au and NT4N/Au interfaces can be summarized to be 0.2 eV and 1.75 eV, which clearly confirm the results obtained in this work.

It can thus be concluded that the interplay of physicochemical, morphological and structural characteristics has a significant influence on injecting contacts of operating OFETs that result to be strongly dependent on the nature of the OSC/metal interface.

CONCLUSIONS

The comparative analysis of n-type OFETs based on NT4N and P13 molecular semiconductors with gold charge injecting electrodes provides an in-depth understanding of the nature of the OSC/metal contact and of its correlation with the electrical characteristics of OFETs.

Specifically, the combination of FT-EXAFS, XANES and computational analyses showed that the presence of thienyl sulphur atoms in NT4N determines the formation of a chemical interaction with the gold electrode. The consequent influence on the electrode formation resulted in small gold nanoclusters perfectly covering the OSC surface. Conversely, in the case of P13 larger gold nanostructures are physisorbed on the organic layer at the early stage of the injecting contact formation.

The XAS experiments on OFETs *in operando* demonstrates that the contact interfacial interactions are stable under device operation, and that NT4N-based OFETs have higher injection voltages in comparison with the P13-based devices.

This work demonstrates that, for device performance optimization, the detailed chemical and structural nature of the injecting contacts must be taken into account. Key features that need to be simultaneously controlled to achieve performing and stable charge injecting contacts are: i) the chemical composition of the metal and the OCS compound, ii) the type of physicochemical interactions occurring at injecting contacts, iii) the interfacial morphology and iv) the structural organization of the metal clusters at the OSC interface.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Device fabrication

Bottom gate-top contact OFETs were realized onto glass/Indium Tin Oxide (ITO) substrates. ITO was used as gate electrode and, a 450 nm thick poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) dielectric layer was deposited on top of it by spin-coating. The OSC was thermally evaporated onto the glass/ITO/PMMA stack with a growth rate of 0.1 Å/sec. In agreement with our

precedent works,^{10,38} the thickness of the OSC layer was set at 15 nm and 75 nm for P13 and NT4N, respectively, in order to have best OFET performance. For a specific test, the thickness of P13 was increased to 75 nm.

Finally, a gold layer with a defined thickness (2 nm, 5 nm, 10 nm, 15 nm, 25 nm or 70 nm) was used for both source and drain electrodes. The electrodes were thermally evaporated onto the semiconductor layer with a growth rate of 0.2 Å/sec. The transistor channel length (L) and the width (W) were 70 μm and 0.12 mm, respectively.

Characterization

X-ray absorption spectroscopy

XAS spectra of the sample were collected at the Dutch-Belgian Beam Line (DUBBLE) at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF), Grenoble. The energy of the X-ray beam was tuned by a double-crystal monochromator operating in fixed-exit mode using a Si (111) crystal pair. The measurements were carried out in inert atmosphere at 25 °C in a suited cell updated with modified hardware to host the metal electrodes to polarize the devices. XAS spectra were collected in fluorescence mode using a 9-element monolithic Ge detector (OXFORD). The in operando spectra were collected at ambient temperature and pressure. The spectra, three scans per electrode type (source or drain), were energy-calibrated and averaged. The model used for the fitting procedure considers gold clusters as ideal cuboctahedra with different dimensions (from 55 to 309 gold atoms).

For XAS measurements under electric field, the operating OFETs were biased at: $V_{GS} = 60$ V, $V_{DS} = 20$ V for the linear regime; $V_{GS} = V_{DS} = 60-100$ V, for the saturation regime.

Electron microscopy

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was conducted using SEM Zeiss Gemini 1530 and Zeiss EVO LS10 instruments. Both instruments are equipped with in-column and ET secondary electrons and BSE detectors and EDS X-ray Spectrometer with SDD detector. The EVO LS10 can be operated in variable column pressure operation mode analysis of samples without preparation and non-conducting ones without surface coating.

Scanning Probe Microscopy

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) topographical images were recorded on a Multimode 8 microscope equipped with a Nanoscope V controller and a type JV piezoelectric scanner (Bruker, USA). Samples were scanned in PeakForce mode with NTMDT-NSG10 probes (Spectrum Instruments, Ireland) in air. Background offset correction and surface roughness parameter calculation were performed with Gwyddion 2.48 (<http://gwyddion.net/>). Root mean squared area roughness (Sq) values are the average of five different $0.25 \mu\text{m}^2$ areas, and the standard deviation of each set of measurements was used as their respective uncertainties.

Simulations

For each of the molecules under investigation, a three-dimensional map representing the spatial distribution of the adsorption energy for a single gold atom was generated. At this purpose, the geometry of an isolated molecule in vacuum was first optimized by DFT by applying the hybrid B3LYP exchange-correlation functional and using the 6-31G* basis set. A cubic mesh of regularly-spaced grid points, with 1 \AA spacing, was then generated around the molecule. A single gold atom was placed in each of the grid points and the energy of the gold-molecule

configuration was computed at the Parametrization Method 6 (PM6) level,⁷⁰ generating a 3D map of the most favourable interaction sites. The minimum energy configuration was further optimized at the B3LYP level, using a LanL2DZ basis set and pseudopotential for gold and a 6-31G* basis set for all other atoms. The whole procedure (grid generation, evaluation of interaction energies on grid points at the PM6 level and optimization of the most favourable adsorption configuration at the DFT level) was iterated five times, thus mimicking the early stages of the formation of the gold-molecule interface. Calculations were performed with the Gaussian 09 program package.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The following files are available free of charge.

EXAFS fitting parameters for both NT4N- and P13-based OFETs at different thickness of the gold electrode, for both source and drain electrodes and for devices in ON or OFF state; Computational simulation of the deposition of 5 gold atoms in the proximity of the NT4N molecule; AFM images of the OSC layer or the electrode, at different thicknesses, for both NT4N- and P13-based OFETs; XANES spectra on NT4N-based OFETs at different electrode thicknesses; transistor electrical characteristics for NT4N- and P13-based OFETs at different OSC or electrode thicknesses.

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The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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